

The role of cardiological and dietary factors in the rehabilitation of young athletes after musculoskeletal injuries

El papel de los factores cardiológicos y dietéticos en la rehabilitación de jóvenes deportistas tras lesiones musculoesqueléticas

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Injuries to the musculoskeletal system in young athletes are one of the most common problems associated with intense physical exertion during the period of active growth. These injuries can have a long-term impact on the physical and psycho-emotional state of the child, hindering further development in sports and reducing the quality of life. It is for this reason that rehabilitation measures must be planned and implemented comprehensively. The authors pay special attention to the role of cardiology in the recovery process, since restorative training and physical activity can have a significant impact on the state of the cardiovascular system. Key aspects are considered, such as the adaptation of cardio exercises for young athletes, taking into account their age and health status, as well as monitoring of the cardiovascular system during rehabilitation. In addition, it is noted that the most important aspect of rehabilitation is a full and balanced diet, which plays a key role in tis-

sue regeneration, muscle recovery and normalization of metabolic processes. Dietary support helps not only to accelerate rehabilitation, but also to reduce the risk of repeated injuries.

The authors study the optimal combination of dietary recommendations and cardio exercises, which contributes not only to the restoration of damaged tissues, but also to maintaining heart health, improving overall endurance and preventing overloads of the cardiovascular system. The main goal is to create a balanced approach to rehabilitation that promotes the safe return of athletes to sports activities.

Keywords: recovery, cardiology, cardio rehabilitation, dietetics, micro- and macronutrients, nutrition, rehabilitation, tissue regeneration, sports medicine, musculoskeletal injuries, young athletes.

Las lesiones del sistema musculoesquelético en deportistas jóvenes son uno de los problemas más comunes asociados con el esfuerzo físico intenso durante el período de crecimiento activo. Estas lesiones pueden tener un impacto a largo plazo en el estado físico y psicoemocional del niño, obstaculizando un mayor desarrollo en el deporte y reduciendo la calidad de vida. Es por ello que las medidas de rehabilitación deben planificarse e implementarse de forma integral. Los autores prestan especial atención al papel de la cardiología en el proceso de recuperación, ya que el entrenamiento reparador y la actividad física pueden tener un impacto significativo en el estado del sistema cardiovascular. Se consideran aspectos clave, como la adaptación de ejercicios cardiovasculares para deportistas jóvenes, teniendo en cuenta su edad y estado de salud, así como el seguimiento del sistema cardiovascular durante la rehabilitación. Además, se señala que el aspecto más importante de la rehabilitación es una dieta completa y equilibrada, que desempeña un papel clave en la regeneración de tejidos, la recuperación muscular y la normalización de los procesos metabólicos. El apoyo dietético ayuda no solo a acelerar la rehabilitación, sino también a reducir el riesgo de lesiones repetidas. Los autores estudian la combinación óptima de recomendaciones dietéticas y ejercicios cardiovasculares, que contribuyen no solo a la restauración de los tejidos dañados, sino también a mantener la salud cardíaca, mejorar la resistencia general y prevenir sobrecargas del sistema cardiovascular. El objetivo principal es crear un enfoque equilibrado para la rehabilitación que promueva el regreso seguro de los atletas a las actividades deportivas.

Palabras clave: recuperación, cardiología, rehabilitación cardiovascular, dietética, micro y macronutrientes, nutrición, rehabilitación, regeneración de tejidos, medicina deportiva, lesiones musculoesqueléticas, atletas jóvenes.

Injuries to the musculoskeletal system are a common occurrence among young athletes, which is associated with increased physical exertion, the characteristics of a growing body and insufficient maturity of bone and muscle structures. These injuries can significantly affect the health and athletic career of young athletes if timely and effective recovery is not ensured. It is known that the degree of regeneration of the child's body is quite high, but nevertheless injuries at an early age require a special approach to recovery, taking into account the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the growing organism and the psycho-emotional state of the child.

The main goal of rehabilitation is the complete or maximum possible restoration of motor functions and adaptation of the child to normal life. Comprehensive rehabilitation includes various methods such as physical therapy, physiotherapy, massage, kinesiotherapy and the use of modern technologies such as robotic simulators and virtual reality. An integrated approach, including dietary recommendations and cardiological monitoring, is of particular importance in the rehabilitation of young athletes. Dietetics plays a key role in tissue repair after injury, providing the body with essential nutrients to accelerate the healing of bones, cartilage, joints, and muscles. Proper nutrition helps strengthen the immune system, which helps prevent complications and speeds up the healing process.

On the other hand, cardiology plays an equally important role in the rehabilitation process. The transition from passive rest to physical activity requires careful monitoring of the state of the cardiovascular system, especially in young athletes, whose organs and systems may react differently to physical activity. It is important to properly adapt cardio loads so as not to overload the heart, as well as to ensure the safety and effectiveness of training.

Thus, the synergy of dietary and cardiological approaches is the basis for successful rehabilitation of young athletes after injuries to the musculoskeletal system. This study will examine how these areas interact with each other, creating conditions for the rapid and safe recovery of athletes' health, minimizing the risk of repeated injuries and returning to active sports activities.

Research methodology. A review of the literature on the role of cardiology and dietetics in the rehabilitation of young athletes after musculoskeletal injuries is based on PubMed and RSCI databases, with emphasis on keywords such as "young athletes", "musculoskeletal injuries", "rehabilitation", "cardiology", "dietetics", "micro and macronutrients".

The main focus was on publications from 2018 to 2024, in addition, attention was paid to sources from 2017 and older, which were of particular importance for this study. Through the use of comparative analysis, various methods of rehabilitation of child athletes with injuries to the musculoskeletal system, such as traditional methods (physical therapy, massage), were compared and the role of cardiology and dietetics in this process was assessed.

The systematic approach allowed us to consider the rehabilitation process as an integrated system, including medical, physiotherapeutic, psychological and pedagogical aspects. The use of this method made it possible to identify the interrelationships between the various stages and directions of rehabilitation and to determine what role dietetics plays in this process.

Playing sports from an early age undoubtedly allows specialists to prepare worthy representatives of the country in the sports arenas of the world. However, heavy physical exertion and intense training invariably leads to injuries of various types, both mild and complex, for young athletes.

Studies conducted by various authors indicate the following. Bikchurin N. M., Takhavieva F. V., having studied the data from one of the sports dispensaries that examined 236 gymnasts aged 7 to 16 years, noted that 22.4% of cases of upper limb injuries were noted among those examined, 21.1% of cases were back injuries, where complaints of pain in the lumbar region largely predominate. spine (12.5%). Young athletes also sought help for post-traumatic pain in the knee joint (11.8%), sprains of the inguinal ligaments (9.9%), and pain in the shin area (3.3% of cases) [1]. Al-Jaberi A.S., analyzing the frequency and nature of injuries to young football players of the Ural Sports Academy football team in Yekaterinburg, born in 2005, 2006 and 2007, consisting of 19 players, noted the following: the frequency of various types of injuries by young football players was quite high, in 2021 almost every player of the team was injured. At the same time, bone injuries accounted for 11% of injuries, muscle injuries – 43%, ligament and tendon injuries – 30%, joint and cartilage injuries – 16%. All of the above also confirms the high level of injury among young athletes[2].

The above trend is noted in the works of not only domestic but also foreign specialists [3,4], while in these works it was noted that the frequency of injuries to child athletes tends to increase. Accordingly, it is extremely important to organize a full-fledged and effective rehabil-

itation and recovery process for children who are professionally involved in sports in order to restore their health.

Prolonged injury leads to sedentary periods that cause a decrease in muscle mass, muscle strength, and function. In addition, muscle atrophy can further prolong the period of return to competition. In this regard, it is necessary to competently organize sports rehabilitation, cardio care, and proper and balanced nutrition.

During the recovery period after injuries to the musculoskeletal system, young athletes may face a number of cardiac problems that arise due to changes in physical activity, age-related development and injury specifics. It is important to take into account that the cardiovascular system at this age is still at the stage of formation, which makes adolescents more susceptible to various cardiac loads and stresses.

Experts point out that after injury and a period of immobility, the athlete's level of physical activity decreases significantly, which can lead to a weakening of the cardiovascular system, a decrease in overall endurance and the ability of the heart to effectively cope with stress. When returning to training, a careful and step-by-step approach to restoring cardio loads is required in order to avoid overloading the heart and blood vessels[5].

During the rehabilitation period, young athletes, especially after a prolonged period of absence of physical activity, may be at risk of developing arrhythmias. Cardiac arrhythmias may be associated with cardio loads that have not been properly adapted. This is especially important in cases where adolescents have hidden or undiagnosed problems with the cardiovascular system, such as myocardial hypertrophy or conduction disorders.

After injuries and limitations of physical activity, athletes may develop problems with venous drainage and blood circulation in general, which often leads to hypotension (a decrease in blood pressure), which is especially dangerous during the recovery period, as the body may not have time to adapt to new loads. In addition, due to hypokinesia and movement restrictions, problems with blood circulation in the lower extremities may occur, which increases the risk of thrombosis.

One of the main problems of cardiology during the recovery period is an incorrect or premature return to intensive training. If an athlete returns to the previous loads without sufficient adaptation of the cardiovascular system, this can lead to overload, an increased risk of injury, and even the development of acute heart diseases such as myocarditis or heart failure.

Thus, cardiological problems in the recovery process of young athletes require a careful approach and professional monitoring. It is important to individualize physical activity, take into account the age characteristics and level of fitness of the athlete, as well as timely conduct cardiological examinations to prevent possible complications.

Discussion. Sports rehabilitation is a therapeutic approach aimed at restoring young athletes, treating their pain, and helping them safely return to sports⁶. The use of sports rehabilitation strategies is essential for the rapid recovery of athletes' health and their return to training and competition. In the early stages of rehabilitation, proper nutrition is crucial to ensure adequate intake of energy and nutrients, prerequisites for wound healing, and management of inflammation and oxidative stress caused by injury.

Cardio rehabilitation of young athletes after injuries is an important component of their recovery, as it includes restoring the normal functioning of the cardiovascular system, adapting the body to physical exertion, and preventing cardiac complications that may occur after a prolonged period of physical inactivity. Since injuries, especially at a young age, are often accompanied by limited physical activity and possible stress on the body, cardio rehabilitation should take into account all the features of the physical and emotional state of adolescents.

After a period of limited activity, when the heart and blood vessels are not regularly stressed, it is necessary to restore their functional ability and endurance. It is important to prevent possible cardiovascular complications such as hypertension, rhythm disturbances, thrombosis, or congestion that may occur due to a sedentary lifestyle during recovery.

Stress, depression and anxiety can have a negative impact on the cardiovascular system, so it is important to take into account the psychological state of the athlete and work with him in parallel with physical rehabilitation. At the recovery stage, regular monitoring of the athlete's cardiovascular system is an important element of cardio-rehabilitation. This may include blood pressure measurement, electrocardiography (ECG) to assess heart rhythm and possible disorders, ultrasound examination of the heart (EchoCG) to assess the functioning of the heart and its structure, pulse oximetry to monitor blood oxygen saturation⁷.

One of the key tasks of cardio rehabilitation is a gradual increase in the intensity of cardio exercises. You should start your workout with light aerobic exercises, such as walking or swimming, so as not to overload your heart. In the future, you can move on to more intense exercises, such as running or cycling, taking into account the physiological capabilities and condition of the patient. Periodic monitoring of pulse, heart rate and blood pressure helps to adjust the load depending on the body's response. It is recommended to exercise at a moderate pace to avoid excessive stress on the heart.

The psychological state of an athlete is also important for his cardiac rehabilitation⁸. The stresses associated with injury and long-term recovery can negatively affect the cardiovascular system. The use of relaxation techniques, psychotherapeutic approaches, and social sup-

port helps reduce stress levels and normalize cardiac activity. Psychological rehabilitation includes working with a coach and a psychologist who helps athletes overcome emotional barriers associated with injury. Proper nutrition plays an important role in cardiac rehabilitation. A balanced diet that includes omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins (especially B groups, vitamin C, E), trace elements (magnesium, potassium, calcium), as well as antioxidants helps not only in tissue repair, but also in supporting heart health. It is important to provide the athlete with sufficient energy so that he can adapt to physical activity⁹.

Cardio rehabilitation involves a transition from light loads to more intense ones, while it is important to monitor the body's response to each stage. After an athlete is fully prepared to increase the intensity of exercise, training should focus on increasing endurance, improving aerobic capacity and overall physical fitness.

It is known that the main goal during rehabilitation is to repair the damaged body part or organs so that the athlete can return to competition. This can be achieved, along with functional and medicinal methods, through proper nutrition, as it improves the recovery process. The most common type of sports injury, which can also lead to immobility and decreased physical activity, is a muscle injury. During muscle recovery, amino acids and proteins, antioxidants, creatine, and omega-3 are given special attention because they prevent muscle loss and promote injury healing¹⁰.

During limb immobilization, up to 0.5-0.6% of muscle mass per day is lost. This leads to loss of strength and neuromuscular degeneration, followed by muscle atrophy. Experts note that athletes need to consume more protein during the training process than is usually recommended (0.8 g/kg per day). During the recovery period after injury or during illness, a higher dose of protein is recommended to ensure maximum muscle protein synthesis – the recommended dose is up to 2.2 g/kg per day¹¹.

During recovery, the type, quantity, timing, and frequency of protein intake should be of key importance. Researchers have determined that whey protein extracts contain approximately the same amount of amino acids and are contained in skeletal muscles in approximate proportions. As the researchers point out, the quality of protein plays a vital role compared to its quantity: for example, after taking 2 g of leucine and 20-30 g of high-quality protein, muscle mass and strength are the same¹². Increasing protein intake during recovery prevents the loss of muscle mass, but it is also noted that when combined with aerobic and resistance exercises, it has a positive effect.

It is assumed that instead of taking dietary supplements, the consumption of protein from whole foods such as eggs, dairy products, fish, legumes and cereals supports the intestinal microflora, and this should be reflected in the diet of young athletes. It is extremely important to balance the daily protein intake, i.e. protein intake for

breakfast should be 31.5 ± 1.3 g, for lunch - 29.9 ± 1.6 g, and for dinner - 32.7 ± 1.6 g, since it enhances muscle tissue synthesis by 25%¹³.

Creatine in the form of creatine monohydrate is the safest and most widely studied dietary supplement. Experts indicate that after taking creatine at a dose of up to 15 g per day for 3 weeks during rehabilitation, there is an increase in myogenic regulatory factor 4 (MRF4), which is responsible for increasing the area of muscle fibers and maximum strength¹⁴. Creatine intake increases the recovery time of a young athlete and increases his performance, increasing the total supply of creatine in the musculoskeletal system by up to 25%. During the supplementation period, creatine monohydrate helps maintain muscle mass, strength and endurance, creatine concentration in muscles, GLUT-4, muscle glycogen, IGF-1, and myogenic regulatory factors.

During muscle repair, inflammation, pain, and swelling occur, and this is unavoidable during tissue repair. Prostaglandin, which is produced from omega-3 fatty acids, is believed to have an anti-inflammatory function and is also responsible for improving blood flow and reducing swelling and pain. These unsaturated fatty acids improve lipid oxidation by acting as antioxidants, which are most abundant in extra virgin olive oil. The researchers note that fish oil consumption reduces muscle loss in injury, and 10 consecutive days of taking fish oil tablets reduce muscle atrophy in immobilized rats, however, no study has examined the same effect on an immobilized human. It is indicated that the consumption of fish oil is useful for reducing muscle mass, but ineffective for gaining muscle mass, it is necessary to determine the necessary dosage in each specific case¹⁵.

Since the maximum mobility of a young athlete's body depends on the joints, joint injuries are the most common type of injury in sports. Sprains, sprains, dislocations, bruises, etc. are common joint injuries in sports. The above injuries can lead to immobilization, as well as affect the athlete's results. Supplements such as collagen, gelatin, and vitamin C help speed up the recovery period after such injuries. In bones, tendons, ligaments, and cartilage, the main structural protein is collagen. Tendons consist of water (about 55-70%) and dry matter (about 30-40%) (consisting of extracellular matrix), of which 60-80% of the dry matter contains collagen (mainly type 1 collagen). It is believed that oral intake of type 1 collagen improves the composition of collagen fibrils in tendons, and hydrolyzed collagen stimulates the regulation of the collagen cycle. According to research results, the consumption of about 10 g of hydrolyzed collagen in the form of supplements per day helps to increase the thickness of cartilage in patients, as well as reduces knee pain¹⁶.

Table 1. Recommended doses of collagen for joint injuries (according to¹⁷)

Injury	Addition	Duration
Joint pain	12 ml of liquid collagen + 5 g of hydrolyzed collagen	Every day for six months
Chronic ankle injuries	3 g of collagen peptide	Daily for six
Damage to tendons and ligaments	5-7 g of hydrolyzed collagen	months daily for three months

Gelatin is used as an ideal additive to eliminate cartilage defects. Using the invitro model, it was proved that gelatin with vitamin C can improve collagen production, since after treating the ligaments with vitamin C and procollagen amino acids, collagen production increased threefold. Experts note that gelatin has a beneficial effect on collagen production in case of injury. In cases where 15 g of gelatin was consumed for 1 hour for a 6-minute skipping rope test, which was performed to stimulate collagen production, a twofold increase in collagen production was recorded¹⁸.

Experts conducted a study on mice using vitamin C to study oxidative stress¹⁹. In the course of this study, it was noted that the number of chondrocytes, fibrous cartilage tissue, and collagen was comparatively increased after 6 weeks, while the content of dihydroethidium and protein carbonyls decreased after 6 weeks. No difference in biochemical activity was observed. This shows that vitamin C reduces oxidative stress and accelerates healing. During rehabilitation, citrus fruits such as kiwi, strawberry, lemon, orange, etc., as well as other foods such as broccoli and pepper should be consumed²⁰.

Injuries caused by bone fractures usually affect the timing of returning to sports, and it is noted that bone injuries in some areas, such as the femoral neck, anterior tibia, and navicular tarsus, are usually associated with a large number of complications. Fractures usually occur due to insufficient intake of nutrients and in those areas of the bones where excessive injury occurs with repeated application of force to this area²¹.

Vitamin D and calcium play a vital role in bone repair, which is essential for the rehabilitation of athletes. According to experts, there is a positive effect on muscle growth and cell differentiation, as well as an increase in calcium absorption by the sarcoplasm, which leads to more intense muscle contractions²².

Vitamin D enters the body under the influence of the sun and with food. In the diet, vitamin D is found in ergocalciferol and calciferol. It has been documented that the intake of 800 IU of vitamin D combined with 2000 mg of calcium per day reduces the risk of fractures²³. Some micro- and macronutrients, such as protein, phosphorus, magnesium, fluorine, and potassium, play an important

role in bone health, followed by iron, silicon, zinc, vitamin A, vitamin C, and vitamin K²⁴.

During rehabilitation, young athletes are recommended to consume sufficient amounts of carbohydrates, fats, proteins and antioxidants, which are beneficial for health. During periods of intense physical exertion, carbohydrates play a vital role in muscle recovery, reducing fatigue, and improving physical performance²⁵. However, the role of carbohydrates in the recovery of the body requires further study.

In addition, it is believed that the microbiome of the gastrointestinal tract can influence nutritional outcomes. 20-60% of young athletes suffer from stress caused by excessive physical exertion and insufficient recovery²⁶. Endurance exercises can affect intestinal permeability, immune response, and inflammation. 16 studies were conducted to identify the role of probiotic supplements in restoring athletes' health, and two such studies provided evidence that probiotic supplements enhance performance²⁷.

The microbiome reduces the side effects caused by antibiotics, as it increases the immunity of the mucous membrane. *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Bifidobacterium* have been found to have a positive effect on immunity, followed by *Bacillus coagulans*, which improve protein absorption. It is believed that consuming chilled probiotics on an empty stomach is more beneficial during rehabilitation. According to research, by modulating

the intestinal microflora, which promotes muscle recovery, positive effects have been observed during vertical jumps²⁸.

Phytochemicals contain different types of herbal ingredients that have different structures that promote positive health effects. Fruit-derived polyphenols improve vascular functions, which leads to improved blood supply to muscles, as well as improved oxygen release²⁹. It is believed that polyphenols play an important role in increasing the athletic activity of athletes. After taking a black-currant supplement, studies have shown an increase in sprinting performance among young athletes. It is also recommended to consume foods rich in polyphenols and chocolate, as it helps reduce oxidative stress and inflammation³⁰.

Phytochemicals reduce muscle soreness and increase recovery time. Consumption of fresh foods rich in polyphenols, such as red fruits, tea, and natural juices, has a much more beneficial effect compared to consumption of concentrated dietary supplements.

For successful rehabilitation after injuries, it is necessary to take into account many factors affecting the restoration of muscle, joint, and bone tissue³¹. A proper approach to nutrition, enriched with essential nutrients, can accelerate the healing process, reduce inflammation, and restore lost functionality³². Below is a table that contains key aspects and nutritional recommendations based on current scientific evidence.

Table 2. Key aspects and recommendations for the organization of nutrition enriched with essential nutrients for young athletes

Aspect	Description	Recommendations
Type of injury	Injuries to muscles, joints, and bones are common.	Muscle injuries (atrophy, weight loss), joint injuries (dislocations, sprains), bone injuries (fractures).
Loss of muscle mass	Up to 0.5–0.6% per day during immobilization.	Increase protein intake to 2.2 g/kg per day, focus on whole foods (dairy, eggs, fish).
Proteins and amino acids	A key element of muscle mass recovery.	Intake of 20-30 g of high-quality protein at one meal; products: dairy, legumes, cereals. The positive effect of leucine.
Creatine	Accelerates the recovery of muscle mass.	15 g per day for 3 weeks; increases muscle strength, muscle creatine volume and GLUT-4 density.
Omega-3 fatty acids	Anti-inflammatory effect, reduction of pain and swelling.	Consumption of fish oil or oil (extra virgin olive oil), the dosage is individual.
Collagen and gelatin	They are important for ligament and joint repair.	5-10 g of hydrolyzed collagen per day, vitamin C supplementation (citrus fruits, berries, broccoli).
Vitamin C	Reduces oxidative stress and promotes healing.	Use with foods (kiwi, strawberry, lemon, orange, pepper, broccoli).
Vitamin D and calcium	They increase bone density and accelerate recovery.	800 IU of vitamin D and 2000 mg of calcium per day; sources: fish, dairy products.
Carbohydrates	They are important for energy recovery.	A full-fledged diet with an emphasis on slow carbohydrates (cereals, cereals).
Probiotics	They restore the intestinal microbiome and promote better protein absorption.	Taking <i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i> and <i>Bifidobacterium</i> ; probiotics on an empty stomach.
Phytochemicals	They reduce inflammation and oxidative stress.	Consumption of fresh fruits (berries, citrus fruits), tea, dark chocolate.
The diet	Optimal distribution of protein intake throughout the day.	Protein: 31.5 ± 1.3 g (breakfast), 29.9 ± 1.6 g (lunch), 32.7 ± 1.6 g (dinner).
Energy balance	The key to successful rehabilitation.	Avoid negative balance; proper nutrition, taking into account all macro- and microelements.

The table shows that for effective rehabilitation after injuries to the musculoskeletal system, comprehensive support of the body through a balanced diet is important. Recovery requires an increased intake of proteins, amino acids, omega-3 fatty acids, creatine, and vitamins (especially D and C). Probiotics and polyphenols also play an important role in maintaining health and accelerating recovery. All these components contribute to reducing inflammation, strengthening joints and bones, as well as improving the recovery processes in the body of young athletes.

Rehabilitation of young athletes after injuries to the musculoskeletal system requires an integrated approach that includes not only physical and physiotherapeutic methods, but also consideration of cardiological factors, as well as specially developed nutrition. The cardiological aspects of rehabilitation are no less important. A period of limited activity can weaken the cardiovascular system, and therefore careful adaptation of cardio loads is necessary in order not to overload the heart. Regular monitoring of the cardiovascular system helps to avoid cardiac complications, such as arrhythmias or hypertension, and ensures the athlete's safe return to physical activity.

A balanced diet is one of the key factors for successful recovery, as it provides the body with the necessary micro- and macronutrients to regenerate tissues, maintain muscle mass, and repair joints, bones, and ligaments. An important role in this process is played by proteins and amino acids, which help restore muscle mass and prevent its atrophy; omega-3 fatty acids and creatine – they reduce inflammation, pain and shorten the recovery period; collagen, gelatin and vitamin C – their role is to accelerate the recovery of joints and tendons.; vitamin D and calcium, which strengthen bone tissue and reduce the risk of repeated injuries. Probiotics and prebiotics, which improve the intestinal microflora, promote protein absorption and reduce the side effects of antibiotics, and phytochemicals that can fight inflammation, reduce muscle soreness and accelerate healing, are also important.

A systematic approach to rehabilitation, including optimally administered cardio loads, consideration of the cardiological status of young athletes, as well as proper diet planning, allows not only faster recovery of the functions of damaged body parts, but also reduces the risk of repeated injury, improving the overall health of patients.

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